

ISic2931

Epitaph of Benantia

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

slab

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.07.02

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Excavations at Ospedale Civile, Siracusa, 1967.11.24

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. □ Memoria Benan
2. ti hic requiscit
3. i[*np*]açę qui bixit
4. anno[s][*□*] qui de[*po*]
5. situs e[*st in*]d(ictione) IIIX □

Apparatus

ann[is]: Lo Faro, Manganaro

Translation

Commentary

Wrongly attributed to the Arangio Hypogeum I by Manganaro

Digital identifiers:

TM 645315

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2012.0623

Manganaro, G. 1993. Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I e VI sec. d.C.. In Calbi, A., Donati, A., Poma, G.(eds.), *l'epigrafia del villaggio*.

Faenza. pp. 543-594. At 585 no.11 fig.28 ph

Lo Faro, Maria Domenica 2010. Osservazioni sugli ipogei di villa Landolina a Siracusa. *Archivio Storico Siracusano*. 45: 11-87. At 58 no.21

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